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CAR-T CELLS: FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH TOTAL AND LONG-TERM REMISSION IN CANCER PATIENTS

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Introduction: Immunotherapies are gaining a great deal of ground in research to cure chronic and even genetic diseases. CAR-T cell therapy has been gaining notoriety for causing some patients to go into complete remission from some types of cancer. **Objective:** To review the literature on total and long-term remission in patients using CAR-T cell therapy. **Method and materials:** This is an integrative literature review, with a reflexive, descriptive and qualitative analysis. We used 6 scientific articles from the following journals: Pubmed, Nature, American Society of Hematology and the following websites: Butantan, Cancer.gov and the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation. **Results:** A substantial number of patients have already been treated in Brazil and around the world using CAR-T cell therapy, many of them are experiencing total remission of the disease, some having had it for more than ten years, however, some of the patients who used it did not adhere to the treatment, the therapy worked partially or had adverse effects, studies show that the factors associated with long-term remissions are more likely to depend on the depth of the initial response to treatment, which is usually quantifiable in the first few months after infusion. **Conclusion:** According to recent studies, patients who achieved a deeper initial response remained in remission for longer than those who did not. Depth can be assessed by measuring circulating tumor DNA; however, more studies are needed along with a longer follow-up period for further clinical confirmation.

Keywords: CAR-T; Oncology; Complete remission.